

OP-AA method

Materials: pipette (1-5 ml), micropipette (10-100 μ L), multichannel pipette (5-50 μ L), amber glass bottles (4 ml, 30 ml), reagent tanks, 96 well plates with UV-transparent flat bottom.

Instrument: absorbance microplate reader (multiskan skyhigh each).

Reagent: ascorbic acid (AA, CAS: 50-81-7), sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium phosphate dibasic (Na_2HPO_4), chelex, ultrapure water.

Preparation of solution:

-Prepare 0.05M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) by dissolving 5.2 g of Na_2HPO_4 and 1.697 g of $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1 L of UP water. Treat PB with Chelex resin (batch method, 6.5 gChelex/L, 24h).

-Prepare 10 mM AA solution by dissolving 0.044 g in 25 ml of UP water.

-Prepare 1 mM AA solution from 10 mM AA solution. Dissolve 300 μ L of 10 mM AA solution in 2.7 mL of UP water.

Plate method:

1^oPreparation of the calibration curve (5 points: 200, 150, 100, 50, 0 μ M AA). Add different volumes of phosphate buffer (PB) to each calibration point (160, 170, 180, 190, and 200 μ L, see Figure 1). 3 replicates for each calibration point.

2^oAdd 160 μ L of each sample into the wells, 3 replicates for each sample (see Figure 1).

3^o Incubate the microplate for 5 minutes at 37°C.

4^oAdd different volumes of 1 mM AA (40, 30, 20, 10, and 0 μ L, see Figure 1) to each calibration point.

5^o Add 40 μ L of 1 mM AA to all samples. Remove visible bubbles.

6^oIncubate the microplate for 1 minute with high-continuous shaking at 37°C.

7^oMeasure the absorbance of ascorbate at 265 nm at 37°C for 2 hours every 2 minutes with 2 minutes with high-continuous shaking.

Calibration curve

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	160 μ L PB + 40 μ L AA	160 μ L PB + 40 μ L AA	160 μ L PB + 40 μ L AA	170 μ L PB + 30 μ L AA	170 μ L PB + 30 μ L AA	170 μ L PB + 30 μ L AA	180 μ L PB + 20 μ L AA	180 μ L PB + 20 μ L AA	180 μ L PB + 20 μ L AA	190 μ L PB + 10 μ L AA	190 μ L PB + 10 μ L AA	190 μ L PB + 10 μ L AA
B	200 μ L PB	200 μ L PB	200 μ L PB	Sample 1			Sample 2			Sample 3		
C		Sample 4		Sample 5			Sample 6			Sample 7		
D		Sample 8		Sample 9			Sample 10			Sample 11		
E		Sample 12		Sample 13			Sample 14			Sample 15		
F		Sample 16		Sample 17			Sample 18			Sample 19		
G		Sample 20		Sample 21			Sample 22			Sample 23		
H		Sample 24		Sample 25			Sample 26			Sample 27		

160 μ L sample + 40 μ L AA

Figure 1. Schematic representation of OP-AA plate with the different reagents added to the different wells.